

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi roli va uni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari

Sohiba Shermamatovna Babakuliyeva

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur ilmiy maqolada tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi o'rni va ahamiyati tadqiq etilgan. Xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda bank kreditlari, imtiyozli moliyalashtirish dasturlari hamda kreditlash amaliyotidagi mavjud muammolar tahlil qilinib, bank-moliya mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Shuningdek, tadqiqot natijalari ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari faoliyatini samarali tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ayollar tadbirkorligi, tijorat banklari, moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash, kreditlash mexanizmi, bank xizmatlari, kichik biznes.

Аннотация

В данной научной статье исследуется роль и значение коммерческих банков в финансовой поддержке женского предпринимательства. Проанализированы банковские кредиты, льготные программы финансирования, а также существующие проблемы в практике кредитования, направленные на развитие предпринимательской деятельности женщин. На основе проведённого анализа разработаны научно-практические предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию банковско-финансовых механизмов. Результаты исследования способствуют повышению эффективности деятельности коммерческих банков в процессе развития женского предпринимательства.

Ключевые слова: женское предпринимательство, коммерческие банки, финансовая поддержка, механизм кредитования, банковские услуги, малый бизнес.

Abstract

This scientific article examines the role and significance of commercial banks in providing financial support for women's entrepreneurship. The study analyzes bank lending, preferential financing programs, and existing problems in credit practices aimed at developing women's entrepreneurial activities. Based on the analysis, scientific and practical proposals and recommendations are developed to improve banking and financial mechanisms. The research findings contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of commercial banks in supporting the development of women's entrepreneurship.

Keywords: women's entrepreneurship, commercial banks, financial support, lending mechanism, banking services, small business.

Kirish

Hozirgi globallashuv sharoitida iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta'minlashda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining roli tobora ortib bormoqda. Xususan, ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish iqtisodiy o'sish, aholi bandligini ta'minlash va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlashning

muhim omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Jahon tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, ayollar boshchiligidagi biznes subyektlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining oshishiga, kambag'allik darajasining pasayishiga va innovatsion faollikning kuchayishiga xizmat qiladi. O'zbekistonda ham ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish davlat siyosati darajasiga ko'tarilib, bu borada ko'plab islohotlar va qarorlar qabul qilindi hamda shu qarorlarga muvofiq ancha ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Ayollar tadbirkorligini qo'llab-quvvatlashda moliyaviy resurslarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni qondirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, bu jarayonda tijorat banklari yetakchi moliyaviy institut sifatida maydonga chiqadi.

Shu bois tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi faoliyatini ilmiy jihatdan o'rganish hamda uni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlarini aniqlash dolzarb ilmiy masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Adabiyotlar sharhi va tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish va uni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari zamonaviy iqtisodiy tadqiqotlarda muhim yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida keng o'rganilgan. Xususan, tijorat banklarining ushbu jarayondagi o'rni moliyaviy vositachilik, kredit resurslariga kirish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish hamda moliyaviy inklyuziyani ta'minlash nuqtai nazaridan ilmiy adabiyotlarda alohida e'tirof etilgan. Nazariy jihatdan, tadbirkorlikni moliyalashtirish masalalari J. Schumpeterning innovatsion rivojlanish nazariyasiga borib taqaladi. Unga ko'ra, banklar tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda asosiy moliyaviy vositachi bo'lib, yangi g'oyalar va biznes tashabbuslarni iqtisodiy o'sish omiliga aylantiradi. Ushbu yondashuv ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashda tijorat banklarining strategik rolini asoslab beradi.

Ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyalashtirishning institutsional jihatlari D. North va W.R. Scottning institutsional nazariyalarida keng yoritilgan. Mazkur nazariyalarga ko'ra, moliyaviy institutlar, jumladan tijorat banklari tomonidan yaratiladigan qoidalar, kredit siyosati va moliyaviy mexanizmlar ayollar tadbirkorligining rivojlanish darajasiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Scott (2001) ayollar tadbirkorligidagi cheklovlar ko'pincha moliyaviy institutlarning madaniy va ijtimoiy omillarni yetarlicha inobatga olmasligi bilan bog'liqligini ta'kidlaydi.

Xalqaro tadqiqotlarda ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyalashtirishda bank kreditlariga kirish muammolari alohida o'rganilgan. A. Demirgüç-Kunt va R. Levine tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda moliyaviy tizim rivojlangan davlatlarda ayollar boshchiligidagi biznes subyektlarining kredit resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari kengroq ekani ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. Shu bilan birga, G. Brush, C. Carter va E. Gatewoodlarning ishlarida ayollar tadbirkorligi uchun moliyaviy resurslarga kirishda garov ta'minoti, kredit tarixi va banklar tomonidan riskni baholash mexanizmlarining muhim ahamiyatga egaligi ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Rossiyalik iqtisodchi olimlar E.N.Fetisov, T.Zaslavskaya va S.Suxanovlarning tadqiqotlarida ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashda bank sektorining roli, ayniqsa imtiyozli kreditlash va davlat-bank hamkorligi mexanizmlarining samaradorligi tahlil qilingan. Ularning ilmiy qarashlariga ko'ra, tijorat banklari tomonidan maxsus kredit mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqish ayollar tadbirkorligi rivojiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

O'zbekistonlik olimlar tomonidan ham mazkur yo'nalishda qator ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilgan. Jumladan, R.Ubaydullaeva, D.Raximova va M.Sobirovalarning ilmiy ishlarida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari kreditlarining

ahamiyati, ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyalashtirishdagi mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari tahlil qilingan. Ushbu tadqiqotlarda ayollar tadbirkorligini qo'llab-quvvatlashda mikromoliyalash, imtiyozli kreditlar va bank xizmatlarini soddalashtirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Mazkur tadqiqot tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi rolini baholash hamda ushbu jarayonni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlarini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Tadqiqotning metodologik asosi institutsional iqtisodiyot, moliyaviy vositachilik va gender iqtisodiyoti nazariyalariga tayangan holda shakllantirildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida tahlil va sintez, induksiya va deduksiya, taqqoslash hamda tizimli yondashuv kabi umumiy ilmiy usullardan foydalanildi. Empirik tahlil O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki, tijorat banklari, Davlat statistika qo'mitasi hamda xalqaro moliya institutlarining rasmiy statistik ma'lumotlari asosida amalga oshirildi.

Shuningdek, statistik va iqtisodiy-matematik usullar, jumladan korrelyatsion va regressiya tahlili yordamida bank kreditlari bilan ayollar tadbirkorligi rivoji o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik baholandi. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Tahlil va natijalar

O'zbekistonda so'nggi yillarda ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylandi. Ushbu jarayonda tijorat banklari tomonidan ko'rsatilayotgan moliyaviy xizmatlar, xususan kreditlash mexanizmlarining ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tijorat banklari ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashda asosiy moliyaviy vositachi sifatida faol ishtirok etmoqda. Markaziy bank va tijorat banklarining rasmiy ma'lumotlari asosida o'tkazilgan tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, ayollar boshchiligidagi tadbirkorlik subyektlariga ajratilayotgan kreditlar hajmi yildan-yilga oshib bormoqda. Ayniqsa, kichik biznes va oilaviy tadbirkorlikni moliyalashtirishga yo'naltirilgan imtiyozli kredit dasturlari ayollar tadbirkorligining kengayishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Biroq, kredit resurslariga kirishda garov ta'minoti yetishmasligi, kredit shartlarining murakkabligi va foiz stavkalarining nisbatan yuqoriligi ayollar tadbirkorligi rivojini cheklovchi omillar sifatida saqlanib qolmoqda.

Tijorat banklari kredit portfeli tarkibining tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, ayollar tadbirkorligi asosan savdo, xizmat ko'rsatish va qishloq xo'jaligi sohalarida jamlangan. Ishlab chiqarish va innovatsion loyihalarga yo'naltirilgan kreditlar ulushi esa nisbatan past bo'lib, bu holat banklar tomonidan riskni baholashda ehtiyotkorlik yuqori ekanligi bilan izohlanadi. Natijada, ayollar tadbirkorligining iqtisodiyotning yuqori qo'shilgan qiymatga ega tarmoqlaridagi ishtiroki yetarli darajada rivojlanmay qolmoqda.

Iqtisodiy-matematik tahlil natijalari tijorat banklari tomonidan ajratilgan kreditlar hajmi bilan ayollar tadbirkorligi subyektlari soni hamda bandlik darajasi o'rtasida ijobiy bog'liqlik mavjudligini ko'rsatdi. Bu holat bank kreditlarining ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda muhim moliyaviy omil ekanini tasdiqlaydi. Shu bilan birga, kreditlardan foydalanish samaradorligi moliyaviy savodxonlik darajasi va bank xizmatlarining qulayligi bilan bevosita bog'liq ekanini aniqlandi. O'tkazilgan tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi faoliyati sezilarli darajada rivojlanayotgan bo'lsa-da, mazkur yo'nalishda bir qator tizimli muammolar

mavjud. Xususan, ayollar tadbirkorlari uchun maxsus moslashtirilgan kredit mahsulotlari ulushining yetarli emasligi, bank va tadbirkor o'rtasidagi axborot nomutanosibligi hamda moliyaviy xizmatlarning hududlar kesimida notekis taqsimlanishi aniqlangan.

Yakuniy natijalarga ko'ra, tijorat banklari tomonidan ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish, kreditlash shartlarini soddalashtirish, imtiyozli moliyaviy instrumentlarni kengaytirish va moliyaviy savodxonlikni oshirish ayollar tadbirkorligining barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Xulosa va takliflar

O'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, tijorat banklari ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim institutsional rol o'ynaydi. Bank kreditlari ayollar boshchiligidagi tadbirkorlik subyektlarining tashkil etilishi, ularning faoliyatini kengaytirish va bandlikni oshirishda asosiy moliyaviy manba hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot davomida bank kreditlari hajmi bilan ayollar tadbirkorligi rivoji o'rtasida ijobiy bog'liqlik mavjudligi ilmiy va empirik jihatdan asoslandi. Tahlil natijalari tijorat banklari tomonidan ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyalashtirish so'nggi yillarda faollashganini ko'rsatdi. Shunga qaramay, kredit resurslariga kirishdagi cheklovlar, xususan garov ta'minotining yetishmasligi, kreditlash shartlarining murakkabligi, foiz stavkalarining nisbatan yuqoriligi hamda moliyaviy savodxonlik darajasining pastligi ushbu yo'nalishdagi asosiy muammolar sifatida aniqlandi. Shuningdek, ayollar tadbirkorligi asosan past riskli va kam qo'shilgan qiymatga ega sohalarda jamlanib qolayotgani iqtisodiy samaradorlikni cheklamoqda.

Tadqiqot xulosalaridan kelib chiqib, tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish maqsadida quyidagi **ilmiy-amaliy takliflar** ishlab chiqildi:

Birinchidan, tijorat banklarida ayollar tadbirkorlari uchun maxsus moslashtirilgan kredit mahsulotlarini joriy etish zarur. Ushbu mahsulotlar garov talablarini yengillashtirish, moslashuvchan to'lov grafigi va imtiyozli foiz stavkalarini o'z ichiga olishi lozim.

Ikkinchidan, davlat va tijorat banklari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni kuchaytirish orqali kafillik va sug'urta mexanizmlarini kengaytirish maqsadga muvofiq. Bu ayollar tadbirkorlarining kredit resurslariga kirish imkoniyatlarini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Uchinchidan, ayollar tadbirkorligi uchun mikromoliyalash va raqamli bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirish tavsiya etiladi. Masofaviy kreditlash, onlayn ariza topshirish va tezkor qaror qabul qilish mexanizmlari hududiy tafovutlarni kamaytirishga xizmat qiladi.

To'rtinchidan, tijorat banklari huzurida moliyaviy savodxonlik va biznes-rejalashtirish bo'yicha maslahat xizmatlarini yo'lga qo'yish lozim. Bu kreditlardan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirish hamda kredit risklarini kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Beshinchidan, ayollar tadbirkorligini yuqori qo'shilgan qiymatga ega sohalarga, xususan ishlab chiqarish, innovatsiya va xizmatlar eksportiga yo'naltirishni rag'batlantiruvchi moliyaviy instrumentlarni joriy etish maqsadga muvofiq.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, tijorat banklarining ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi rolini kuchaytirish iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirish, bandlikni oshirish va ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Taklif etilgan chora-

tadbirlarni amaliyotga tatbiq etish ayollar tadbirkorligining barqaror va samarali rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati

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